

The Progress on Geology, Geophysics, and Geochemical Competency Standards Application in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

The development of the geothermal industry in Indonesia is still far from expectation. The government strives to increase geothermal capacity by attracting investors in this sector, but the results are still not significant. Several problems hinder investors, including high exploration risk, remote locations with minimal facilities, complicated policies and permits, and a less targeted national energy master plan (Ermawati & Negara, 2014). One of the government's initiatives to mitigate risks in this industry is to minimize potential risks made by human error by setting competency standards for workers in the geothermal industry. Indonesia has implemented national competency standards (NCS) in various fields of work. However, many positions still have no competency standards, especially in the renewable energy industry until recently. The new NCS in Geology, Geophysics, and Geochemical (3G) of the geothermal industry has been prepared by the Directorate General of New and Renewable Energy in 2016 and approved by the Ministry of Manpower in 2018. This step is also directly followed up by the Human Resources Development Agency of the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources (MEMR). The personal certification body of MEMR has prepared a certification scheme as a basis for competency tests. Currently, the scheme has been submitted to the National Professional Standards Agency to obtain a license to carry out certification following the existing NCS. This paper is focused on answering several questions related to NCS in 3G before being implemented in the industry. The first part of the paper discusses the main reason and steps taken before the NCS establishment. Furthermore, this paper elaborates on the need for NCS in the industry and steps to implement it. This paper also discusses the industry's feedback for the implementation of the NCS that is mostly positive.

1. INTRODUCTION

The geothermal energy utilization for electrical generation in Indonesia started when the first geothermal well drilled in 1926 in Kamojang, West Java. However, after a lengthy study, the Kamojang geothermal power plant (GPP) is just operated in 1983. To date, less than 10% of resources have been utilized primarily for geothermal power plants.

Presidential Decree No. 22/2017 regarding the National Energy Plan confirms that available geothermal resources' potential is very abundant. The resource is estimated at 23,965.5 MW, consisting of 9,339 MW resources and 14,626.5 MW reserves, as shown in Table 1. RUEN (2017) also targets 23 percent renewable energy in the energy mix by 2025. This target includes 16% of geothermal energy utilization or around 7,241.5 MW.

Table 1. Potential and geothermal energy installed in Indonesia 2017 (RUEN, 2017; MEMR, 2019; Geological Agency, 2019)

No	Location	Resources (MW)	Reserves (MW)	Total (MW)	Installed (MW)
1	Sumatera	3,833	5,846	9,679	744.3
2	Java	2,455	5,652	8,107	1,253.8
3	Bali	91	244	335	0
4	Nusa Tenggara	338	1,025.5	1,363.5	12.5
5	Kalimantan	169	13	182	0
6	Sulawesi	1,727	1,341	3,068	120
7	Maluku	651	505	1,156	0
8	Papua	75	0	75	0
Total		9,339	14,626.5	23,965.5	2,130.6

1.1 Geothermal Human Resources

An abundant supply of skilled labor must support the high government targets for geothermal development in Indonesia. The workforce requirements include geologists, geophysicists, geochemists. Other professionals are also required, such as drilling experts, technicians, hydrologists, and other skilled personnel for operations and maintenance. This human resource must be prepared before starting a geothermal field development project.

The government, Directorate General of New, Renewable Energy, and Energy Conservation (DG-NREEC), is responsible for supervising and controlling human resource management in all geothermal developers. The directorate is also obliged to ensure that local workers obtain competency development by transferring knowledge from both foreign workers and more experienced Indonesian workers (DG-NREEC, 2019). The capacity development might come through a series of human resource development programs that aimed to ensure that workers can master the competencies needed in geothermal industry activities. Workforce requirements are closely related to workforce planning needed in a project. Therefore, human resource planning must be carried out carefully because human resource needs significantly affect the amount of investment needed.

The requirements for geothermal specific skills and training include technical and science and cover various technical skills. The number of people needed is vast, especially at the drilling and construction stage, covering all skills and the general workforce. However, in practice, unskilled labor tends to be much higher, partly due to social reasons.

1.2 The National Competency Standard in Indonesia

Indonesian National Competency Standards (NCS) are the formulation of work capabilities that cover aspects of knowledge, skills, and expertise. The NCS also covers work attitudes that are relevant to the implementation of assigned tasks and conditions. The NCS in Geology, Geophysics, and Geochemical (3G) was developed by the MEMR in consultation with relevant industries to ensure the suitability of workplace needs. The NCS is used primarily to design and implement job training, conduct training assessments, and evaluate the latest level of skills and expertise possessed by personal. The Minister of Manpower determines NCS with the following objectives:

- As a reference for competency-based education and training.
- As a reference for the implementation of competency certification.
- As a reference for structuring the company
- As a reference for the preparation of the company Standard Operating Procedure.

Ministry of Industry (2019) described that NCS contains a collection of competency units. The competency unit is the result of identified competency needs in the workplace. Each competency unit is part of the workplace requirements, such as knowledge and skills for work performance, including those related to occupational safety and health, literacy skills, and basic mathematics. The competency unit must accommodate the diversity of the industrial sector, companies, and workplaces. In other words, competency units are arranged based on the similarity of work standards found in various similar workplaces. The competency unit may not refer to the use of specific equipment or brand specification. The competency unit is not a detailed procedure needed to carry out a job because work procedures can vary from one workplace to another.

The content of the competency unit illustrates the following:

- The outcome of a specific job
- The conditions under which the competency unit is implemented
- Knowledge, skills, and work attitudes needed to achieve work results according to standards
- Evidence that can be collected to determine competently or not yet competent.

The competency element is the fundamental of a competency unit. The combination of each element of competency forms a competency unit as a whole. The competency element describes the process of a coherent work carried out in one competency unit. The competency element must be an activity that can be carried out, observed, and assessed. The elements are arranged using active sentences, preceded by verbs before objects, and in the form of direct and straightforward statements. Each competency unit consists of at least two competency elements.

Further, the performance criteria describe the performance to be achieved in each element of competence. The criteria are formulated to evaluate skills, knowledge, and work attitude. The criteria are measured work implementation results to determine what will be assessed from a competency unit's performance achievements.

On the other hand, to measure the competency of personnel, a competency assessment is needed. BNSP (2013) explained that the assessment guide contains an explanation of various conditions or circumstances that can guide the assessment process. The guide can also be used to assess competency units, both during training and competency testing. BNSP (2013) also detailed that the assessment guide explains the following matters:

- Assessment context: explains the things needed in the assessment. This context also explains the conditions that affect the achievement of work competence. The context also includes "where, what, and how" the assessment should be done.
- Competency requirements: explain the competency units that must be mastered/fulfilled before (if needed) as the initial requirements needed in continuing to master the competency unit.
- Required knowledge and skills: information and knowledge needed to support the achievement of performance criteria in the competency unit.
- Required work attitudes: information on work attitudes must be displayed to achieve performance criteria in the competency unit.
- Critical aspects: explain the aspects or conditions that significantly affect or determine the competency unit's successful implementation.

2. NCS FORMULATION

2.1 Competency Need

The geothermal project is a long development process through several stages (Gehring & Loksha, 2012; Hervey et al., 2014). A research center partly carries out one of these stages under the MEMR, namely preliminary and exploration surveys, to calculate geothermal resources (Umam et al., 2020). At this stage, geologists, geochemists, and geophysicists should conduct active surface and subsurface surveys to estimate key reservoir parameters. The data include temperature, depth, area, mineralized zones, and permeability. They also integrate all aspects of geoscience-related to geothermal systems to create conceptual models that guide exploration, drilling, and further geothermal development management.

The next step is the drilling test. This stage is generally carried out by the geothermal company working in the area to confirm the reservoir's existence, exact location, and potential. This stage is also referred to as the most expensive stage in geothermal projects with the highest risk. The geologist is responsible for assisting and overseeing drilling, geological logging, analyzing and interpreting the core, determining well productivity, and determining the drilling depth.

Furthermore, a geothermal company carried out the stage of project review and planning, field development, power plant construction, and commissioning after getting positive results from drilling. In this stage, the geoscientist assists civil work such as power plant site preparation or piping network arrangement. Geotechnical engineers and near-surface geophysics are also required to identify and mitigate geohazards' risk.

The last stage of developing the geothermal field is operation and monitoring. Steam engineers, operators, technicians, reservoir modelers, geologists, geochemists, and geophysics experts are needed at this stage. Umam et al. (2019) mentioned that geoscientists are responsible for monitoring surface activity and potential contaminants (water and gas). They also need to conduct down-hole surveys, testing of production wells, and evaluating injection wells. They are responsible for geochemical and geophysical analysis, including micro seismic.

2.2 The development of NCS in Geology, Geophysics, and Geochemistry

The NCS in 3G is arranged through the following stages:

2.2.1 Team initiation and formation

The initiation of NCS preparation was carried out by the Directorate of Geothermal and Center for Human Resources Development Center for Electricity, New and Renewable Energy and Energy Conservation (HRDC-ENREEC) as representatives of the government. This initiation was carried out by considering the need for a new NCS in the geothermal field because, until recently, there are no competency standards in 3G, especially in the geothermal field.

The initiation of NCS preparation was submitted to the Competency Standards Committee to assess and justify the suitability of demands for it. The needs of NCS are assessed based on industrial systems and/or technical regulations, the standards development master plan. After being declared eligible, the Competency Standards Committee incorporates the proposal in the annual formulation plan. The competency standards committee forms a formulation team and a verification team for the formulation of NCS in the geothermal sector.

2.2.2 Formulation of Draft NCS in 3G

The formulation of the NCS in 3G draft was carried out using field research methods and compiled using the Regional Model Competency Standard (RMCS) model. The RMCS is a competency standard model introduced by the International Labor Organization (ILO) to develop a competency standard. This model uses a functional approach to the work processes of a similar business or industrial activity. ILO (2006) explained the basic concept of competence in RMCS is to focus on what is expected of the workforce at work besides the learning process or the time spent during training or education. The competency standard that developed based on RMCS should meet the requirements as follows:

- Connect with actual practice in the current workplace;
- Expressed as outcomes; and
- Written in clear, simple, easy to understand language that is ready to be understood by workers, employers, trainers, supervisors, and trainees.

2.2.3 Verification by the Competency Standards Committee

The verification team verified the NCS draft in 3G made by the formulation team. The NCS draft (NCS-D) verification is carried out with structural criteria and following applicable regulations. The substance of the NCS-D has been formulated clearly, precisely, and accurately. It is capable of being traceable to work process standards in the geothermal industry. The NCS draft that has met the verification criteria is identified as the distribution of NCS draft phase 1 (NCS-D1).

2.2.4 Preconvention

NCS-D1 is validated through a pre-convention organized by the competency standards committee followed by relevant stakeholders, including industry elements, practitioners and/or experts, industry associations, professional groups, educational and training institutions, professional certification bodies, the Ministry of Manpower, Agencies of National Personnel Certification (ANPC), as well as the DG-NREEC. The results of the pre-convention to be further corrected by the drafting team. Then, it is submitted for verification by the Directorate of Competency Standardization of the Ministry of Manpower.

2.2.5 Verification by the Ministry of Manpower

The Ministry of Manpower conducted verification of NCS-D1 results of the pre-convention before the national convention. NCS-D1 that has fulfilled the verification criteria is identified as NCS draft phase 2 (NCS-D2) to be subsequently submitted to the DG-NREEC as material for implementing the national convention.

2.2.6 National Convention

NCS-D2 is standardized through national conventions that participated by related stakeholders. They are including industry personnel, practitioners, industry associations, professional groups, training institutions, professional certification bodies, Ministry of Manpower, ANPC, and agencies that technically related.

2.2.7 Determination by the Minister of Manpower

The Ministry of Manpower then examined the NCS draft phase 3 delivered by the DG-NREEC for its completeness and suitability. The Minister of Manpower finally determines the NCS in 3G, which has been declared complete and appropriate.

2.2.8 Enforcement by the Minister of Energy and Mineral Resources

After being determined by the Minister of Manpower, NCS is submitted by the Minister of Energy and Mineral Resources to be enforced compulsorily or voluntarily.

2.2.9 NCS Review

A review on NCS in 3G is carried out by the Competency Standards Committee at least once in 5 years or as needed to maintain validity and reliability. The NCS review results could be in the form of recommendations for changes, revocation, or without modifications.

3. THE IMPLEMENTATION OF NCS ON 3G

3.1 The NCS in 3G Content

The NCS in 3G, which has been prepared by the MEMR and then endorsed by the Ministry of Manpower, must be passed down to a curriculum before it can be used for competency-based training. Each training institution or educational institution can carry out this process by using the NCS as a reference. On the other hand, the certification body of personnel needs to draw up a certification scheme and obtain approval from the ANPC before conducting certification.

The personal certification body of MEMR proposes certification schema for three positions, each for geoscientists, geophysicists, and geochemists regarding NCS in 3G. The submission of the certification scheme to ANPC must be accompanied by competency test material along with the assessment method used. Generally, the certification process starts with a written test to get a value from the aspect of knowledge. Further, the certificate taker must take a practical or simulation test to show his skill. The final test is an oral test or interview to confirm the written test results and an oral examination to determine the graduation certificate.

The competency assessment test material commonly asked the first time is about Safety, Health, and Environmental Protection (HSE) due to its vital role in the workplace. Other materials should be referred to as the content of the NCS in 3G showed in the tables below. Table 2. shows three levels of geologist position, Table 3. shows the level of geophysicist position, and Table 4. shows the level of geochemist position.

Table 2. Levels of geologist base on the certification scheme of LSP BPSDM.

Junior Geologist	Geologist	Senior Geologist
Comply with the Basic Principles of HSE in the workplace	Analyze the basic principles of HSE in the workplace	Evaluate the basic principles of HSE in the workplace
Measuring compliance with the Basic Principles of HSE at work	Make reports and work plans for activities at work	Creating geological geothermal models
Conduct Effective Communication at work	Manage geothermal geological databases	Choose tentative and conceptual models of geothermal systems
Conduct a Geological Survey of Geothermal Areas (Reconnaissance)	Make tentative or conceptual models of geothermal systems	Recommend estimates of geothermal potential
Conduct a Geological Mapping of Geothermal Areas	Doing Wellsite Geology work	Estimating the sustainability of drilling well operations
	Recommend planning for geothermal exploration well drilling	Recommend planning for geothermal exploration well drilling

Table 3. Levels of geophysicists base on the certification scheme of LSP BPSDM

Junior Geophysicist	Geophysicist	Senior Geophysicist
Determine the position on the map and field	Creating geophysical models of geothermal systems	Creating an integrated geophysical model
Conduct a geoelectric survey method	Interpret geophysical models of geothermal systems	Calculate the geothermal potential
Carry out a gravity method survey	Plan geophysical survey strategies and technologies	Decide on exploration strategies and assessment of geothermal potential from exploration well data.
Conduct a geomagnetic method survey	Monitor petrophysical measurements	Planning the development and production of geothermal fields
Conduct a survey of electromagnetic methods	Recommend planning for geothermal wells	
Conduct a survey of microearthquake (MEQ) method or Passive seismic		

Table 4. Levels of geochemists' base on the certification scheme of LSP BPSDM.

Junior Geochemist	Geochemist	Senior Geochemist
Recognize the basic principles of HSE in the workplace	Measure the level of compliance with the basic principles of HSE in the workplace	Evaluate the basic principles of HSE in the workplace
Comply with the basic principles of HSE in the workplace	Receive and understand relevant information from several sources	Linking and gathering information from several oral and written sources

Junior Geochemist	Geochemist	Senior Geochemist
Receive and understand effective communication at work	Search for and select information related to from several sources	Evaluating early models of geothermal geochemistry
Take a sample of manifestations	Processing sample data	Update geothermal geochemical models based on the latest well data
Interpret sample data from manifestations	Take geochemical samples of wells	Creating a sustainability strategy for geothermal fields
	Interpret geochemical sample data wells at initial conditions	
	Monitor geochemical wells	
	Plan geothermal wells based on geochemical geothermal models	

3.2 Feedback from Stakeholders

A survey for the implementation of NCS in 3G in Indonesia was conducted in December 2019. These survey results are used to provide an overview of the acceptance of the 3G NCS, which will begin to be implemented in 2020, especially in competency-based training and 3G Geothermal certification. Several questions were asked to measure the acceptance of the NCS in 3G before being implemented in the form of competency-based training and personnel certification. The correspondents of this survey are geothermal stakeholders from the government, namely the Center of Human Resources Development for Electricity, New Renewable Energy and Energy Conservation, the Center for Mineral Resources, Coal and Geothermal, and the Directorate of Geothermal, Directorate General of New and Renewable Energy, Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources. Further, the correspondents have also come from geothermal contractors and companies, namely Star Energy, PT Geo Dipa Energi (Persero), and Medco Power. Questionnaires were distributed online (online) from 26 December 2019 to 10 January 2020.

The survey question begins with the general requirement for geothermal staff. In the initial stages, developing a geothermal working area includes a preliminary survey, exploration, and test drilling. The survey concluded that operators' general competencies are basic geology, geothermal exploration, basic drilling operations, HSE in geothermal fields, geosciences, drilling engineering, reservoirs engineering, social engineering, reserve estimation, regional geology outline.

Further, all respondents agreed that the capacity development method needed to obtain these competencies is through training, workshop, and job training. On the other hand, the way to measure the competency acquired or owned is by competency test, certification, and assignment, which can be in the form of written tests or interviews.

Moreover, the survey found that the application of NCS is essential as a minimum standard of competence and to understand the baseline parameters of the skills needed to carry out the required activities. Also, NCS is vital so that competencies are standardized in all places, industry, education, or government.

The government is committed to supporting the development of Indonesia's geothermal industry while minimizing risk and hazard. According to most respondents, the application of NCS will not hamper or become an obstacle for the geothermal industry as long as there is a discussion process involving the industry when formulating NCS in 3G. The experts also suggest that NCS can also be a tool for selecting and measuring. The people involved and the activities carried out have clear and appropriate references.

As mentioned above, in preparing the NCS in 3G, the government has involved stakeholders, including Industry, Association, and Universities. The government must consider several things before enacting this mandatory NCS. The main thing is the socialization to each of these stakeholders for a certain period before implementation. The government can also carry out a phased trial followed by an evaluation of the trial results. This effort is needed to obtain the industry's input as the main actor to ensure it aligns with current industry needs.

Finally, the survey conveyed that after implementing NCS in Geothermal 3G, several NCS areas were proposed by respondents. The proposed NCS includes fluid flow testing, reservoir technicians, resource calculation, and geothermal reserves.

3. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The MEMR continues to improvise to support the development of the geothermal industry in Indonesia. Several efforts are set, such as minimum competency standards for geothermal workers to ensure labor efficiency and company assets' safety. The latest competency standards set by the MEMR are NCS for geologists, geophysicists, and geothermal geochemists. It is hoped that the implementation of NCS is for geothermal companies and government personnel handling geothermal. Other parties the need to be certified are higher education in geology and all relevant stakeholders.

The MEMR has implemented the NCS in 3G recently, which is currently drafting a certification and ratification scheme from ANPC. According to the survey of the acceptance of the NCS in 3G, comments from the stakeholders are generally positive and fully support implementation. The survey results also show that there is still much homework done by the MEMR in the future. These work include preparing the new NCS and more active outreach to the public, especially geothermal industry players.

The development of the geothermal industry is still as slow as it is today. Hence, MEMR is expected to continue to look for solutions together with stakeholders, including the efforts to develop human resources. Furthermore, aside from MEMR homework to implement the new NCS in 3G, other NCS arrangements also need to be developed in the future. For example, there are still no competency standards for steam field operators, geothermal drilling operators, production operators, and well management in the geothermal field. On the other hand, stakeholders are also expected to support this government initiative to provide certified

competent workers in the geothermal industry. The main objective of this venture is to reduce the level of risk and, in the long term, reduce investment costs, thereby growing the industry.

REFERENCES

- BNSP: Agency of National Personnel Certification Regulation Number: 03 / BNSP.302 / X / 2013 concerning Guidelines for Issuance of Competency Certificates [Peraturan Badan Nasional Sertifikasi Profesi Nomor: 03/BNSP.302/X/2013 Tentang Pedoman Penerbitan Sertifikat Kompetensi] (2013).
- DG-NREEC: Directorate General of New, Renewable Energy, and Energy Conservation Performance Report 2018 [Laporan Kinerja Ditjen EBTKE Tahun 2018], Directorate General of New, Renewable Energy and Energy Conservation, Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources (2019).
- Gehring, M., Loksha, V., Geothermal handbook: planning and financing power generation. ESMAP technical report; no. 002/12, Washington, DC: World Bank (2012). Retrieved from https://www.esmap.org/sites/esmap.org/files/DocumentLibrary/FINAL_Geothermal%20Handbook_TR002-12_Reduced.pdf; <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/396091468330258187/Geothermal-handbook-planning-and-financing-power-generation>.
- Geological Agency; Executive Summary Update on Geothermal Database and Resources in 2019 [Executive Summary Pemutakhiran Basis Data dan Sumber Daya Panas Bumi Tahun 2019] (2019). Retrieved from <http://psdg.geologi.esdm.go.id/images/stories/neraca/2019/exsumpanasbumistatus2019.pdf>
- Hervey, Colin; Beardsmore, Graeme; Moeck, Inga; Ruter, Horst; Bauer, Stefan; Best practices guide for geothermal exploration. Washington, D.C.: World Bank Group (2014). Retrieved from <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/190071480069890732/Best-practices-guide-for-geothermal-exploration>
- ILO: Guidelines for Development of Regional Model Competency Standards (RMCS), International Labour Organization. Regional Skills and Employability Programme in Asia and the Pacific (SKILLS-AP) (2006). Retrieved from http://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---asia/---ro-bangkok/documents/publication/wcms_bk_pb_234_en.pdf
- Kemenperin: Indonesian National Work Competency Standards. Ministry of Industry [Standard Kompetensi Kerja Nasional Indonesia. Kementerian Perindustrian], Jakarta (2019). Retrieved from https://kemenperin.go.id/kompetensi/NCS_idx.php
- MEMR: PRESS RELEASE NUMBER: 705.Pers / 04 / SJI / 2019 Date: 17 December 2019, Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources of the Republic of Indonesia 'Muara Laboh PLTP Phase One Operates, West Sumatra Electric Supply Increased [SIARAN PERS NOMOR: 705.Pers/04/SJI/2019 Tanggal: 17 December 2019, Kementerian Energi dan Sumber Daya Mineral Republik Indonesia' PLTP Muara Laboh Tahap Satu Beroperasi, Suplai Listrik Sumatera Barat Makin Andal] (2019). Accessed on December 31, 2019, from <https://www.esdm.go.id/id/media-center/arsip-berita/pltp-muara-laboh-tahap-satu-beroperasi-suplai-listrik-sumatera-barat-makin-andal>
- RUEN: General National Energy Plan [Rencana Umum Energi Nasional], An attachment of Presidential Decree Number 22/2017 (2017).
- Ermawati, T., Negara, S. D.: Pengembangan Industri Energi Alternatif: Studi Kasus Energi Panas Bumi Indonesia. LIPI Press, Jakarta (2014). Retrieved from <http://www.penerbit.lipi.go.id/data/naskah1424834930.pdf>
- Umam, M. F., Nugraha, H. S., and Fathoni A.: The Geothermal Capacity-Building Initiatives by the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources. Proceedings, The 7th Indonesia International Geothermal Convention & Exhibition (IIGCE) 2019, Jakarta (2019).
- Umam, M. F., Susilo, J., Purba, D. P., & Adityatama, D. W.: Design of Geothermal Drilling Training Curriculum as the Implementation of the National Competence Standard on Onshore Drilling, In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 417, No. 1, p. 012016). IOP Publishing (2020, January). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/417/1/012016>

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

3G	Geology, Geophysics, and Geochemical
ANPC	Agencies of National Personnel Certification [BNSP]
DG-NREEC	Directorate General of New, Renewable Energy, and Energy Conservation [Dirjen EBTKE]
GPP	Geothermal power plant
HRDC-ENREEC	Human Resources Development Center for Electricity, New and Renewable Energy and Energy Conservation [PPSDM KEBTKE]
HSE	Safety, Health, and Environmental Protection
ILO	International Labor Organization
MEMR	The Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources
NCS	National Competency Standards [SKKNI]
NCS-D	The NCS draft
NCS-D1	NCS draft phase 1
NCS-D2	NCS draft phase 2
RMCS	Regional Model Competency Standard